

34°0'0"E

35°0'0"E

36°0'0"E

37°0'0"E

38°0'0"N

38°0'0"N

37°0'0"N

37°0'0"N

50 25 0 50 km

Projection: UTM 36N
 Datum: WGS 1984
 SRTM: CGIAR-CSI v4.1